

Comicubes - A playful tool to stimulate (design) creativity

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Abstract This paper investigates the play potential of an open-ended and hybrid play concept: Comicubes – a platform for play, play-testing and simultaneously tool to stimulate (design) creativity. We propose a hybrid concept that interweaves the ideas of comics and three-dimensional toys together. The concept challenges the traditional idea of comics as images that are read one after another by suggesting a more open reading paralleling the interpretation and use of and a physically manipulable toy object. The concept introduced in the paper, combines the two-dimensional serial image with a three-dimensional and therefore more open-ended toy medium – the cube. Moreover, the concept invites integration of digital enhancements in the physical plaything and thus enables potential AGE (Augmented Game Experience) elements.

Keywords *Creativity, Game, Augmented game experience (AGE), Play, Hybrid toys*

Introduction

The paper at hand introduces, investigates and tests the play(ful) potential of a concept we have named Comicubes. Our hypothesis is that Comicubes could be used as not only a hybrid plaything including elements familiar from both toys and games, but furthermore, a tool to stimulate (design) creativity.

The Comicubes concept intertwines several areas of interest to the society: play technology creativity and Augmented Reality (AR): The prototype introduced in this paper consists of 24 double-sided cardboard cubes with different information layers on the sides of each cube, including letters, words, onomatopoeic utterances and different kinds of images. Moreover, Comicubes further includes an Augmented Reality element, which may be accessed through a smart phone application.

The concept of *Comicubes* introduced in the paper is rooted in the wooden block puzzles of the past but carries a resemblance to a popular storytelling play concept of past years, namely, Rory's Story Cubes and an open-ended 'sandbox' game, *Minecraft*¹. However, despite its simple cardboard construction, our concept presents wider opportunities for more complex and interactive storytelling. Further, the AR dimension enables a straightforward connection to digital media, enabling screen-based hybrid social play (Heljakka 2016).

In conjunction with the idea of comics, this plaything evolves potentially into a toyish and/or gameful concept, which invites its user to both open-ended and hybrid play patterns. The paper continues the work of the first author with an interest in the 'the mediation of things and the thingification of media' (Lash & Lury 2007), the hybrid relations of both physical and digital toys, games and their connections to transmedia, image-based storytelling and finally, play.

Comic artists Lynda Barry and Scott McCloud have

pondered upon the nature of play. For Barry, playing is about 'not knowing'. In other words, playing presents an activity, where one is predisposed to expect the unexpected. In Barry's idea, play is 'one of the oldest, most complex, and most tightly integrated of all ecosystems' (Barry 2008, 11), which should not only be seen through the lens of fun. Adults often mix up the idea of play with happiness, but as Barry explains, there can be a kind of amnesia about the seriousness of playing (Barry 2008, 51). Through playing, we may bring something alive. A playful, imaginative take on reading comics, especially in regard to ones telling stories about characters, is crucial. If the juxtaposed images and texts created by comic artists would not be able to breathe life into their characters by activating a reader's imagination, they would probably fail on many levels.

Play is in fact a form of meta-communication, a way to express a playful state of mind. To play is to explore and to react to the world and its actors – language, images, objects and other people's behavior through our senses, cognitively and emotionally. We engage in play because it is a joyous activity, which energizes us. Sometimes playing connects with everything we do and sometimes, when a pattern of behavior is evoked by a playful object. One central aspect of toys is that they make us curious about their characteristics. In comics, what feeds our curiosity is both the personalities of characters and what happens to them as the plots of the stories unfold. Openness to interpretation intrigues the imagination when reading

1 For Rory's Story Cubes, see <https://www.storycubes.com/>. In digital games such as *The Sims* and *Minecraft* the patterns of play are open-ended as compared with the traditional notion of games as rule bound systems of play. In *The Sims*, says Stein, we can understand each instance of gameplay as constructing a narrative that the player both follows and authors (Stein, 2006, 259).

Figure 1. The Comicubes prototype box.

Figure 2. The Comicubes concept consists of 24 folded and two-sided paper cubes (or boxes), which can also be opened.

comics and playing with toys. In our suggestion, the openness of both forms of storytelling may be increased by hybridization.

Theoretical background: Play, creativity and storytelling

Together, creativity, storytelling and tangible media, stimulate creativity through play. Play has universal dimensions, but also culture-specific aspects (Smith 2010, 95). Huizinga (1992, 19) states that “Play is older than culture, for culture, however inadequately defined, always presupposes human society, and animals have not waited for man to teach them their playing.”

Huizinga defines play as voluntary activity in which people set the terms and timing of their own involvement. Second, play is distinguished from routine affairs by its absence of material consequences. Third, play is separated from other activities through its use of rules, spaces, ideas of time, costumes, and equipment. Fourth, play both honors rules and encourages transgression. Finally, play can promote participants bonding together in “secret” (Heljakka 2013, 194; Henricks 2008, 159). According to Follet (2007), play is often associated with “winning” pleasure emotions (Lieberman 1977; Zimmerman 2003). The Comicubes concept promotes play as a voluntary activity and invites one to involve in open-ended play with the material.

In Western society, ‘creativity’ is most commonly used to refer to the embodied cognitive process that gives rise to pieces of music, paintings, poems and other things that are taken or presented as art. Creativity is heavily dependent on the nature of the creator and it is also intensely context-dependent: reproducing the style or exercise of style replication. Margaret Boden (1990) introduced exploratory creativity, where the conceptual space being explored is fixed (though possibly not all visible, and possibly infinite) and exploration occurs within that space (for example, different songs in a particular style), and transformational creativity in which the space itself is subject to change (developing from one style to another). (Boden 1990) Thus, we see that the production of the Comicubes per se is not what guarantees its value: while of course, the artifact must

exist to be valued, it is interaction between production and (probably, at least initially, introspective) evaluation by a user, and then by a social user group, that identifies relative value and relative novelty, of both the artifact and the way it was made. Thus, we can decompose creativity into a series of steps and test within a process, of which a ‘creative’ agent is capable, and can begin to study it. This is altogether more scientifically tractable than the philosophical debate about the ineffable nature of creativity itself.

Stories include narratives that serve as schematic structures. According to Mandler (1984, 22), stories exist in the background, bottom, or part of a structure and remain relatively unchanged regardless of content or genre. One of the basic human means of experiencing the world is through stories. The quality of a story derives both from life and processes of reflection. Within stories, narratives serve to guide and provide a structure for a listener or reader. With regard to games, to engage in a narrative as a player is to be drawn into participating with a story (Clandinin 1989). In Comicubes the concept itself is the story and one has the possibility to create stories of one’s own by using the Comicubes concept as a playful tool.

Comicubes: A hybrid playful concept

The Comicubes concept introduced in this paper describes an experimental plaything, a hybrid combining sequential art with a physical, three-dimensional play-object, or toy. As argued earlier, it is interesting to see how hybridization has occurred in contemporary play material and applications. Hybridity may occur in many ways in a plaything. Examples of levels or dimensions of hybridity in games and toys have been explored e.g. by Heljakka (2012) and Tyni et al. (2013). When discussing the hybrid affordances of the Comicubes concept introduced in this paper, it is therefore also interesting to reflect upon its possible connections to game-like objects and play patterns associated with them. The Comicubes concept consists of two versions, A and B. In both versions of Comicubes², we utilize 24 foldable cardboard cubes with 6 sides each. Altogether, in the one-sided version this makes 144 sides, and in the double-sided version 288 sides of information layers to fill with either images (such as

photographs) or text (letters, onomatopoeic utterances or words), or, as in classical comics, juxtaposed and serial images together with text.

‘Comics is a mono-sensory medium. It relies on only one of the senses to convey a world of experience’, says McCloud (1993, 89). On the contrary, the Comicubes concept as a *multisensory* play concept also invites the reader to manipulate/rotate/organize-stack/build sequences of the parts in either random order or according to the reader/player’s wishes.

‘Playing is about not knowing’, claims Lynda Barry (2008). Hypothetically, Comicubes, as a multi-sensory play medium, affords various play patterns: it allows the player to explore, organize and display it like building blocks; to arrange, rotate, stack and display its pieces by animation of the player’s hands. Compared to animation which is sequential in terms of time, comics are spatially juxtaposed (adjacent, side-by-side) (McCloud 1993, 7). The images and texts and combinations of them in each frame and side of a cube allow both an animated manipulation, juxtaposed arranging of them and in this way, nonlinear narrative construction. Instead of being an *automaton*, an object presenting autonomous movement, or a pre-animated experience, the Comicubes require actions associated with *object play* (see e.g. Smith 2010), i.e. tangible exploration. In other words, the player gives movement to the object and through his/her act of play decides the arrangement of these sculptural (cardboard cube) pieces.

The Comicubes, as seen from the perspective of this paper, is a research instrument and potential playful tool that may stimulate creativity, which allows exploration of dimensions of its playability, play patterns and play value. Through a test pilot study, described in this paper, we seek answers in order to understand both the nature of the envisioned concept and the processes, which evolve around it, once put into play. We suggest that the Comicubes concept invites the user to play with it and can therefore be seen as a potentially playful object. Further, the Comicubes gives the comic story a toyish dimension and thus more narrative openness than a reader of a traditional comic is used to. Moreover, this transfiguration brings into discussion both the affordance and the play-value of the proposed object, the potential plaything.

Hypothetical play patterns of Comicubes

The Comicubes come packaged in a cardboard box (Figure 1), which can also be used to arrange the cubes. On the other hand, and contrary to the idea of a traditional puzzle, the cubes should also invite to play happening ‘out of the box’, outside of the grid constituted by the frame of the box. Moreover, as an artefact aiming at as open patterns of play as possible, the Comicubes should also invite to play that does not involve all 24 cubes, but perhaps only a few of them, paralleling the idea of a short comic strip that only utilizes some frames to tell a story. In this way, this exploratory ‘comic-toy’ does not restrict itself to a strict 3D format that would run its course in one glance or purely visual engagement. Instead, the

artefact invites its user to manipulation, exploration and otherwise imaginative reception – in other words – invites the recipient to playful engagement with itself offering a new way to experience elements constituting several potential stories in 24 pieces. At the same time, the toyishness and play-value should be communicated on the level of one Comicube only, whereas the storyness is enriched by adding more cubes to the player chosen and constructed set.

There are many ways to manipulate the cubes. Movement is essential in how the player will access the images and texts displayed: The player may ‘read’ one cube at a time, moving from one side of the cube to another, simultaneously turning around the cube. Alternatively, one may organize the cubes either in horizontal or vertical arrangements, in formations familiar from comics; ‘strips’ or panels, by creating series of frames consisting of any number of cubes between 2–24.

We have constructed an introductory video presentation about some of the hypothetical play patterns the Comicubes concept holds (see: <http://youtu.be/sRGss4sVF-4>).

Toyish playability: Open-endedness

De Valk et al. have explored open-ended play with interactive objects in multiple studies (see e.g. de Valk, Bekker and Eggen 2013). According to their studies, open-ended play provides a player with the freedom to construct his/her own rules, goals and meaning. Thus, open-ended play designs offer interaction opportunities as a trigger for creating personalized games. We must keep in mind that even ‘seemingly limitless open-play scenarios, include implicit or explicit rules that establish behaviour’ (Flanagan 2009, 252). In other words, eventually, rules are even created in open-ended or toyish type of play.

The open-endedness of Comicubes limits itself on one hand in terms of its physical dimensions. On the other hand the visual and textual information in the frames of the cubes is equally limited. However it is in the creativity and playful attitude of the reader to decide where the limits for arranging the cubes are. In other

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- 2 One their one side, the 24 Comicubes in the first prototype come with six comics ‘stories’ divided in the following themes; 1) The history of comics, 2) The history of toys, 3) Onomatopoeia (classical examples from the history of comics), 4) The dancing doll, 5) A toy comic developed by the concept designer of Comicubes and 6) Arguments from this research paper articulating, explaining and developing the concept. The colouring of the ‘photoplay’ (toy photographs) is toyish in nature, whereas the argumentation follows a more subtle tone. One their reverse side the 144 frames come with either a letter of the alphabet or a key word. In this way, the reverse side of the Comicubes affords to be played like a more elaborate set of alphabet blocks.
 - 3 “Every successful children’s action fantasy, like Pokémon, like Superman, is also an organizing fantasy”, see Jones (2002, 223).

words, Comicubes is constrained in its design due both to its materiality and capacity to communicate visual and textual clues.

How does Comicubes differ in its artefactuality and openness to play as compared to for instance a puzzle or a brainteaser? A classical puzzle, a jigsaw, usually builds up around the idea of one correct solution, one that is most often communicated visually on its packaging. We may see this visualization as the fundamental explicit rule of how to 'play' in the right way. On the other hand, a traditional jigsaw puzzle, due to the form of its pieces can only be assembled in one way without breaking the pieces. On the contrary, the Comicubes does not require its parts to be assembled in any particular way. Nor does the concept require the reader to use a regular die or any other device in order to decide the order of cubes. Of course, this does not exclude the option of using additional elements such as other toys or objects, however, if the player so decides. Although the cubes can be organized in any way the player decides, the designed affordances are built upon the idea of the human tendency and desire to see meaning in structure and organizing. This parallels to what Jones (2002) calls 'organizing fantasy' known from the actions of collector-type players who get enjoyment from both the arrangement of their collected objects (e.g. creating displays) and in their minds, building up a data bank of information about these objects found in various sources, e.g. in the realms of fandom.³

The Comicubes box, which functions both as a storage space for the plaything(s) may also be seen as a frame, a Huizinga magic circle of play that both signals 'this is a thing to be played with' and communicates the affordance of using it to organize and reorganize the cubes in seemingly endless combinations of the 24 cubes and their two sides, which means 6⁴⁸ (over octillion) different combinations to be more precise. The player may only use some of the cubes in order to create comic strips, or play with the complete set by using the either the sides of a particular comic 'series' or by mixing them.

Gameful playability: Constructive co-operation
'Gaming is people-oriented' (Ståhl 1987, 16) and many forms of play are enjoyed because of the social aspect. As the number of players who may manipulate and organize Comicubes simultaneously is not restricted in any way, the concept can be situated either in the categories of single-player or multiplayer and thus social, even co-operative play. As such, the concept differs from traditional comics, which are usually read by one reader at a time. When considering their physical dimension, toys are traditionally not seen as socially shared objects as compared to e.g. board games. Instead, two players may play in parallel with similar toys.⁴ However, as a potentially shared plaything, Comicubes presents the possibility of collective and co-operative play in the name of open-ended, non-linear storytelling, providing the players with a visual, narrative and tactile, multiplayer play experience. As a conceptual platform, Comicubes is also a content distribution device, allowing different character licenses and their various

story worlds to be used. Moreover, the possibility of seeing Comicubes as a *construction toy* opens up new ideas on potential ways of organizing the cubes and categorizing it as a hybrid plaything featuring familiar characteristics of both puzzles and building blocks.

Games are fundamentally experiential, explains Mary Flanagan (2009, 184). Ståhl divides games into entertainment games, educational games, experimental games and research games (Ståhl 1987, 34). We assume that the Comicubes concept is not only a potential hybrid between comics and toys, but also a hybrid of an experiential and research type of a *game* (system). Experiential games aim at testing theories or hypotheses without having an application in mind. It is because of its hybridity that the Comicubes concept is experiential. In other words, without play testing it, it is impossible to understand and to report to outsiders what the players think of it in terms of a playful object about its play value, *playability* and possible unexpected affordances. On the other hand, the concept can be potentially understood as a research game, a game 'with the purpose of obtaining empirical material'. When test-played and documented, this potentially playful artifact will also generate empirical material that can be later applied in designing new toy/game experiences.

Hybrid playability: Augmented Game Experience (AGE)

Hybridization between forms of entertainment media has interested scholars of various playthings, both digital and physical. In recent times, games have made an entry to numerous other forms of entertainment and areas with more utilitarian functions. Gamification, as a sub-phenomenon of the *ludification* and parallel to the emerging *toyification* of culture (Heljakka 2014, 2015), refers to the application and use of game elements in 'apps' outside of the gaming context.

MR (mixed reality) systems cover the extensive continuum between reality and virtual reality (Azuma 1997, 20). In practice, MR (mixed reality) systems are implemented as AR (augmented reality) systems, in which a real world environment is augmented with digital (virtual) objects, or as AV (augmented virtuality) systems, in which a virtual environment is augmented with real objects. As a result, AR or AV systems use user interactions with both real and virtual objects to enhance user perceptions and experiences (Tråskbäck, 2004, 13). The concept of the Comicubes could create digital content, which extend storytelling to next level. Augmented reality technology give great possibilities to open virtual world for one side of the comic, which can be anything for example a picture, alphabet, sign or QR code. And using camera phone with augmented reality application you can open the virtual world and get your story for next level. The digital content could

4 For 'parallel play' see Smith, P. K. (2010) *Children and Play*, Wiley-Blackwell, United Kingdom and Parten, M. (1932) "Social participation among preschool children", *Journal of Abnormal and Social Psychology*, 27, 243–269.

Figure 3. The Comicubes offer a platform for potential AGEs.⁵

be a 3D picture, video or animation.

By adding an AGE (augmented game) element to Comicubes it may become a hybrid multiplatform plaything that acts between material and digital worlds. Concretely this means that the cubes can be read by a mobile application, which scans the edges of the cubes and takes the user to different digital environments. This added material can be for example videos, music, photographs, text and/or links. It may be even possible for Comicubes users to first document and then communicate with each other using this application and share their experiences and creations. The possibilities that this digital addition creates are limitless and promising.

Method

Experimental design

As Engeström (2006) observes “play can be employed as a method in design. For example, playful techniques can be used to study users and conceptualize the idea of a new product. These techniques may include diary keeping, storytelling, scenario building, and creating visual collages. A future product may be visualized using drama, cartoons, short movies or toys.” When developing the Comicubes hybrid play concept solely for entertainment, or with ulterior motives such as co-creation, social experience or emotion experience and feedback, designing an enjoyable experience remains one of the most important aspects. In the evolving area of the gamification development in the context of creative education, finding new challenges for creativity processes has recently emerged. The aim of our pilot study was to introduce the Comicubes concept as a creative tool for users and to find out more about its potential to function first as 1) a toy, 2) a game and 3) a hybrid of the aforementioned and second, as a tool for stimulates (design) creativity.

Participants and play testing

The Comicubes concept was tested with a group of students. There were totally 9 participants (4 female and 5 male), all of who have played board games. Our participants’ age distribution was between 21 to 37 years. All participants are students at the University of Turku.

We designed the following experimental setup as illustrated in Figure 4. The subjects first got

Figure 4. Experiment Setup for this study.⁵

conditioned to a certain level of understanding Comicubes. Then the testers assigned to create their own model of the concept. They chose the technique by using equipment (scissors, markers, white/blank cubes) and created their own version of the Comicubes concept. Two researchers and one assistant operated the experiment. One guided the subjects in the role of giving lecture on play-oriented design and giving the assignment, and other undertook the interview (gave instructions for filling survey) observed the situation and ensured a stable treatment throughout the experiment. During the experimental task data was collected using video recording when users played with the Comicubes. In every step of the experiment, the time was tracked but time constraints were not imposed on subjects.

The two phases were carried out during two days. On the first day the students participated together in a lecture on playful design, which introduced the concepts of toy, game and hybrid. The students then were given the individual task of creating an individual play concept of their own consisting of four cardboard cubes.

The students needed to fill out a preliminary survey. After filling out the preliminary survey, users underwent the main test. The study was conducted in two phases: First, the students completed a design task by designing their own, individual play concept based on cardboard cubes. After the user test, participants filled out an evaluation form. Second, the students were given the task to, in pairs, interact with the original Comicubes prototype and to evaluate its play potential and play value by answering structured questions and listing all possible play patterns that

5 To communicate the possibility to use AGE enhancements for Comicubes, the prototype has been given an information layer by using Qualcomm Vuforia for Unity. In order to unlock the embedded information, a mobile application is needed

came to their mind while exploring and manipulating the cubes for 10 minutes. The results of the questionnaire are demonstrated in the following.

Initial results of the pilot study

The Comicubes pilot user test final evaluation sheet has 5 separate parts. The first part evaluates the practical benefits of the concept, which focused on its potential as a creative tool. The second part evaluates the concepts adaptability to function as a social co-creation tool, which is at the same time an individual tool for user. The third part evaluates Comicubes diversity for using the concept as professional peoples’ creation tool or as one a user could add other material like toys to. The fourth part evaluates the manageability of the Comicubes with users’ skills in playing. The fifth part of the evaluation sheet includes open questions.

In the first part, we wanted to know how the participants experience the concept’s practical benefits. We have three statements, from which the user needed to choose the best to describe their opinion. We have used a five-point Likert-type scale, which is used to measure attitudes using the following options: Strongly agree, agree, neither agree nor disagree, disagree, strongly disagree. As such, the scale purports to measure direction (by agree/disagree) and intensity (by strongly or not) of attitude.

According to Albaum (1997), with some questions regarding attitudes, a person must compute an evaluative judgement, whereas, with others, such a judgement is simply retrieved. In a real sense, we can view an opinion a verbal expression of an attitude, which means that opinions are the means we have for measuring attitudes (Albaum 1997).

In the *first part*, the assumed practical benefits include that the Comicubes concept provides a real benefit to creativity training, in promoting creative thinking, for example the implementation of users’ creativity. The first part includes some open questions: Is it easy to create own Comicubes hybrid concept?, What things do you like mostly Comicubes hybrid concept design? Did Comicubes hybrid concept designing respond your expectations?, Could you actually play or use Comicubes hybrid concept in your studies or research to support your work? The *second part* we have claims on Comicubes hybrid concepts (Empirical findings of claims is shown Table 1.). The third part discusses which are the main user groups to use the Comicubes hybrid concept. The *third part* also discusses how participants did share their Comicubes hybrid concept ideas with other users.

Results show that the participants of the pilot testing phase of the Comicubes hybrid concept mostly say that the making of the concept was easy. Participants

Table 1. Empirical findings of claims on this study.

Arguments	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither disagree nor agree	Agree	Strongly agree
Practical benefits					
I think that I could play and take advantage of this Comicubes hybrid concept in regularly.	22,2%	22,2%	22,2%	22,2%	11,1%
I think that Comicubes hybrid concept is too complicated.	44,4%	44,4%	0%	11,1%	0%
I think the Comicubes hybrid concept is easy to understand and play.	0%	22,2%	22,2%	44,4%	11,1%
Adaptability					
I think the different functions of a Comicubes hybrid concept are connected to each other successfully and the digital dimension has been utilized.	11,1%	55,6%	33,3%	0%	0%
I believe that most will learn to use and exploit the Comicubes hybrid concept containing a digital dimension as well quickly share content on the Internet (social media)	0%	22,2%	44,4%	11,1%	22,2%
Diversity					
I think the Comicubes hybrid concept is suitable for children.	0%	0%	00%	50%	50%
I think the Comicubes hybrid concept is idea for working as a tool in the creative industries.	11,1%	0%	11,1%	44,4%	33,3%
Manageability					
I felt very confident in designing and playing Comicubes hybrid concept.	0%	33,3%	0%	33,3%	33,3%
I think learning to use the Comicubes hybrid concept requires additional guidance.	11,1%	22,2%	22,2%	22,2%	22,2%

Figures 5, 6 and 7. Students test-playing Comicubes: “Are the rules somewhere in here?”; “If this is a game, who wins?”; “This is a research-cube-puzzle-comic”.

also see that developing an idea into a prototype is easy, but *“the emergence of ideas was easier than turning them playable format”*. Participants liked most the development of their own concepts visual, using their creativity and designing for comics. Participants see that, *“its limitations, the paper and the build blocks really gave impetus to work, “what these can do?”*. Result show that participants didn’t have many expectations of the Comicubes hybrid concept. Participant’s comments include that *“there were no expectations. Slightly disconcerting was that what this even is. Is this some kind of technique to create new ideas for games and toy design of an overseer?”* Participants see that they could easily to use Comicubes hybrid concept for their hobbies, studies and maybe even work. Participants see, that one *“could image using it for a training course, but not my studies or work in this moment”*. The result of Comicubes hybrid concept claims summarized in Table 1, which provides a suggested outline of empirical findings.

Results present that participants understand the Comicubes hybrid concept as a multifunctional platform. Participants found that different combinations and the play scenarios in relation to Comicubes could be presented in a social media environment. Participants stated that if the idea is good than they could introduce their concept in social media. Participant present that *“I would introduce the concept because I, in any case make videos about playing. Implementation would be anonymously on YouTube, without the player into anyone’s identity is revealed”*. Participants present that the main target group of the Comicubes hybrid concepts are: children, students, innovation hunters, researchers and artists. Participant’s comments also included, that this Comicubes hybrid concept *“seems to be some kind of Game Jam –brainstorming technique”*.

Conclusions

In this paper, we have introduced the first version of the concept for the hybrid play instrument called Comicubes which combines and creates a mash-up of comics and toys, but also seems to be a hybrid of an open-ended storytelling device, a construction toy (or puzzle) and an experimental and research type of a game (system). Furthermore it may be considered a tool that stimulates creativity. We acknowledge the playability and play potential of the initial physical prototype, as it allows comic-style storytelling to extend itself over previous boundaries of its traditional format and in this way opens up new

possibilities for open-ended play usually associated with three-dimensional toys. Furthermore, we see potential added play value in reference to AGE elements, which can be added to the cubes graphically and read from them digitally through the use of mobile applications.

According to the results of our pilot study conducted with 9 university students and the presented analysis, it is possible to say that new elements for example digital platforms, augmented reality technology and other social media services could easily be added to the Comicubes concept. Participants liked the idea that Comicubes offers the possibility of being used simultaneously by multiple users. This could extend to experiences related to challenge and social experience, as using social interaction is the driving force in gameplay, which Comicubes also envisions. Preliminary results indicate that a combination of pleasurable and creative elements causes a sense of deep enjoyment so rewarding that participants feel that manipulating Comicubes is considered a concept one may simply enjoy in order to have a creative experience. Additionally, an important precursor to a playful way to create Comicubes is to match between a person’s creating skills and the challenges associated with the task, with both being at a certain level. Most flow or immersion experiences occur with activities that are goal-directed (as in this user test), bounded by rules, and require mental energy and appropriate skills. The study’s participants felt that creating Comicubes concepts offered them stimulation and a surprising way to create a concept of their own. How much of the enjoyment associated with the use of Comicubes, besides its gameful qualities, is dependent on its open-ended – or toyish – nature needs further assessment.

In future research we will investigate more deeply the design implications for our conceptual playful tool, presented in this paper.

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